

CONCEPT OF INDIAN MANAGEMENT IN UPANISHAD

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Abstract:

Corporations, educators, bureaucrats and all those who carry a heavy workload around the world are increasingly questioning the same paradigms of efficiency, goal achievement, control and analysis, hierarchy and authority for finding more human and wisdom oriented strategies. It is now being recognized that the mind management or the self management is central to managerial qualities and responsibilities. Wisdom from the ancient sources can be of immense help in gaining the required clarity for experiencing the joy of management. A New Manager with the help of wisdom and meditation can release blocked physical and emotional energy allowing one to attain greater health, inner peace and professional success.

Key Words: Management, Mind & Peace

Introduction:

Definition of Management -Management is a group activity: Management is not an isolated individual activity but it is a collective activity or an activity of a group. It aims at using group efforts for achieving objectives. Managers manage the groups and coordinate the activities of groups functioning in an organization.

- According to D. E. McFarland, "Management is the distinct process by which the managers create, direct, maintain and operate purposive organisation through systematic, co-coordinated and cooperative human efforts"
- According to Gemp R. Terry, "Management is a distinct process consisting of planning, organising, actuating, and controlling, performed to determine and accomplish objectives by the use of people and other resources".

The Upanishads are the last section of the Vedas considered and known as the Vedanta. There are many Upanishads, but ten of them are the principle ones, and commentaries have been written on them by the great Adi Sankara. The Upanishads are a collection of 108 philosophical dissertations. Out of all the Upanishads, the following eleven are considered to be the topmost: Isa, Kena, Katha, Prasna, Mundaka, Mandukya, Taittiriya, Aitareya, Chandogya, Brihadaranyaka, and Svetasvatara. These are some of the important lessons of life that the Upanishads teach us. They also teach us several other spiritual truths. This great quote from the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad which we chant everyday:

Asato ma sad gamaya
tamaso ma jyotirgamaya
mrutyor ma amritamgamaya
From ignorance lead me to truth
From darkness lead me to light
From death lead me to immortality

Indian Ethos Management:

Oxford defines ethos as "The characteristic Spirit and Beliefs of community / people" which distinguishes one culture from the other. Indian ethos is drawn from the Vedas, the Ramayana, Mahabharata, the Bhagwadgita, and Upanishads. Right from the Vedic age it has been discovered two basic universal truths of life.

- The essential infinitude and divinity of all souls.
- The essential oneness and solidarity of universe and all life.

The first truth was expressed UPNISHADA as:

AHAM BRAHMASI (I am Brahman)

Or

AYAM ATMA BRAHMAN i.e. The Individual soul is Brahman

Or

TATTWAMASI (Thou art that).

This is the first truth thought to every child. Even a poor uneducated man living in a hut knows that God is in everybody and therefore there is sameness in all. The second truth is about a holistic universe. Where at a level of pervading consciousness everything is interconnected at VYASTHI LEVEL (Individual level) my limbs, hands, legs, ears, eyes, heart, lungs.... Everything are me. I live in all of them. Their sorrows and joys are

my sorrows and joys. Similarly at SAMASTHI level (the whole universe) I am not a single individual but I am a part of the whole universe just as my limbs are part of me.

Modern science has accepted that in this holistic universe all minds and matters are interconnected at a deeper level. The basic unity of life cannot be broken. Love, sacrifice therefore emerge as the only for a meaningful living. On the basis of this holistic vision, Indians have developed work ethos of life. They found that all work, physical or mental, managerial or administrative have to be directed towards single purpose. The manifestation of the divinity in man by working for the good of others, for the happiness of others. These Indian ethos are required all over the world in present scenario in managing business and industry effectively and efficiently.

As stated in the Bhagwad Gita, the ultimate goal of life is not earning money and building up properties but to attain the state of ananda or bliss. To achieve this state, one has to have peace within is heart, mind and soul. Peace is the most covetable possession on the earth. It is the greatest treasure in the universe. Peace is the most important and indispensable factor for all growth and development.

Peace is a state of quiet. It is freedom from disturbance, anxiety, agitation, riot or violence. It is harmony silence, response, rest. Peace is the natural state of mind. It is his birthright. In today's world people have literally everything: a sweet home, car, sufficient money to survive, luxuries to fulfill their desire but still they do not have peace. Money can't give us peace. We can purchase many things, but we cannot purchase peace. We can buy soft beds but we cannot buy sleep. We can buy good food, but cannot buy good appetite. We can buy good tonics but we cannot buy good health. We can buy good books, but we cannot buy wisdom.

Through inner peace, a manager can have a healthy relation with his customers and suppliers since every person likes to interact with a happy go lucky person rather than a person who is mentally disturbed, the best and efficient decisions are made only when someone is at mental peace since such a person can analyze all the alternatives in effective manner.

A manager can easily motivate his employees and workers as he will be loved by everyone through his peaceful nature and he can very well teach them the concept of Karma Yoga, which states "Yogah Karmeshu Kaushalam Samatvam Yogah Udyate" i.e. he who works with calm and even mind achieves the most. Thus he can bring out higher productivity with effective use of resources. He would have good relations with his boss and colleagues. Most importantly, he would have great relations with his wife and other family members. He would have a good health since the basic root of all diseases is worry or tension.

Five Elements of Corporate Governance:

Governance is everywhere. As we all know, our universe is governed by 5 elements of nature:

- Land
- Water
- Air
- Fire
- Sky

Without these elements, really, there is no life. The elements of nature bring in different assets to our existence. Our ancestors have acknowledged these and we all know their importance.

Land: Being Grounded

Corporate need to be grounded and look at things as others sees them.

- Only when Corporate are grounded, they fuel other elements of corporate governance.
- Fundamentals of Corporate Governance are about dealing with the ground realities from all the stakeholders' perspectives including the employees

Water: Being Flexible

- Being Adaptive and Flexible.
- Understanding matters deeply than looking at its surface'
- Getting the taste of what is being guided and governed

Air: Invisible Presence

Governance is all about not knowing that you are being governed. To me, that's the highest level of governance; it should be as simple as electricity flowing from the switch, water flowing from the taps. No drama! Just silently going through the motions of doing what it does. Governance needs to be invisible yet exist everywhere like air. It should transmit the sounds of governance to the right levels as to the true attribute of air which transmits sound and it will show its color if something is mixed up.

Fire: Destroying Evil

This is the ultimate weapon. Fire absorbs the good and destroys the evil. The only attribute of this element is that, it can be seen, Evil forces that act will always see the fire behind them waiting to destroy them. Another quality of fire is it leaves no trace of what it destroys. Corporations should have the fire to clear the evil forces that hinders the growth of the Organization. The governance should be structured in a way that it is clearly seen as a lethal weapon to all the destructive forces.

Sky - Endless Possibilities

Even in utmost turmoil, one thing that holds us together is Hope and the endless possibilities. History shows many instances of this quality. If we observe closely, when you try to reach the sky, it expands itself infinitely. Men have traveled farther to moon only to understand the limitless possibilities that sky brings in. We know we cannot capture it we can only appreciate and acknowledge it. The rule is very simple - The possibilities are endless. Sky is the limit.

Conclusion:

From the above discussions we conclude that much of modern management principles existing today can be derived from the body of knowledge of the ancient Indian scriptures. However, in practice, the sustainability of the existing management frameworks is still dubious. And through the wisdom of Ancient Indian scriptures, we can make the existing modern management paradigms more sustainable in practice. Through spirituality wisdoms of the Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, etc. we can not only promote a more ethical and responsible leadership on an individual or institutional level but also move towards the direction of restoring World peace and a better world economic order through coupling globalization with spiritual congruence. It is time that modern management thinkers should embrace the importance of ancient Indian ethos in filling the gaps that exist in the existing paradigms of leadership and management. Modern Management through Ancient Indian Wisdom: towards a more Sustainable paradigm

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